

Beyond Accuracy: Building Trustworthy Extreme Events Predictions Through Explainable Machine Learning

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Abstract:

Extreme events, despite their rarity, pose a significant threat due to their immense impact. While machine learning has emerged as a game-changer for predicting these events, the crucial challenge lies in trusting these predictions. Existing studies primarily focus on improving accuracy, neglecting the crucial aspect of model explainability. This gap hinders the integration of these solutions into decision-making processes. Addressing this critical issue, this paper investigates the explainability of extreme event forecasting using a hybrid forecasting and classification approach. By focusing on two economic indicators, Business Confidence Index (BCI) and

Consumer Confidence Index (CCI), the study aims to understand why and when extreme event predictions can be trusted, especially in the context of imbalanced classes (normal vs. extreme events). Machine learning models are comparatively analysed, exploring their explainability through dedicated tools. Additionally, various class balancing methods are assessed for their effectiveness. This combined approach delves into the factors influencing extreme event prediction accuracy, offering valuable insights for building trustworthy forecasting models.

Keywords: *Extreme events prediction, explainable machine learning, class imbalance.*

Introduction

Extreme events have attracted huge attention of researchers last few decades considering their two-edged threat: small number but large in impact which poses a particularly difficult quandary (Chen, Gupta, and Tragoudas 2022; Ghil et al. 2011). Studies on the topic cover their summarization, detection, and prediction in different areas such as finance, weather, etc

(Zhao 2020). On the aspect of their prediction, with the large amount of data generated day-to-day, machine learning (deep learning) is seen as a game changer due to its ability to capture hidden patterns in data to generate accurate predictions, which represents the major limitation of the statistical approach. Thus, powerful frameworks have been developed to provide better results in this scope of studies. However, techniques applied in forecasting of

Extreme Events are generally in their infancy and mostly domain specific and despite the large advances achieved in their forecasting resulting from the use of machine learning techniques, the crucial difficulty lies not so much in finding new prediction methods but in finding ways to trust these predictions. The available literature considers mostly the improvement in forecasting accuracy such as in (Ding et al. 2019) which propose improvement in forecasting of extreme events considering the extreme value loss instead of the quadratic loss. The analysis and prediction of the outbreak of corona virus is proposed in (Petropoulos and Makridakis 2020) where machine learning was able to unveil hidden valuable information to detect future outbreak of the pandemic. Due to the imbalance classes in the prediction of extreme events, a technique based on block resampling in joint predictor forecast space is proposed in (Chen et al. 2022). While these studies propose various outstanding approach to improve accuracy in the prediction of extreme events, they lack to give insight in the importance of explainability of these models applied in the case of extreme events forecasting. It is becoming more complex for humans to interpret these models considering their increasing complexity. This situation has the potential to affect their confidence in the integration of those solutions into the decision-making process (Wu et al. 2021; Zhao 2020) despite their outstanding performance. This justifies this paper which addresses the aspect of the explainability of forecasting of extreme events using the hybrid forecasting and classification approach, which aimed to determine whether the events in a close future is a normal or extreme. This approach deepens one's understanding on why and when the prediction of extreme events in a forecasting and classification aspect should be trusted. A case study focused on two crucial lagging indicators in economics and business: the Business Confidence Index (BCI) (Anon n.d.-a) and the Consumer Confidence Index (CCI) (Anon n.d.-a) is considered. These indices, often used to gauge consumer and business sentiment within a specific period, can fluctuate in tandem and

influence significant economic events like downturns, job losses, and financial stress (Anon 2014; Bielova, Halík, and Ryabushka 2021; Juhro and Iyke 2020; Teresiene et al. 2021). Our goal is to utilize these indices to predict their joint trend for the next month and determine whether it indicates an economic downturn (extreme event), based on a pre-defined threshold. This threshold defines values below it as representing an extreme event and values above it as normal. To achieve this, the remaining of the paper consists in section I which is the introduction followed by section II which deals with the methodology and explanation of different concepts considered in this research. Section III is dedicated to the result and discussion and the last section IV is the conclusion.

Methodology

Definition

Hybrid Forecasting Classification at Glance

This forecasting method applied in extreme events combines two forecasting approaches, regression and classification, using either one or multiple models on either univariate or multivariate forecasting approach to answer the question related to the forecasting of events in the future and the detection of extreme events in that predicted future (X. Chen et al., 2022; Ghil et al., 2011; Zhao, 2020).

Divided in two stages (Figure 1), this technique, in the scope of this study, consists first, after data acquisition and preprocessing, in defining the threshold that defines events through a defined labelling, here zero as normal event and one as extreme event. A formal supervised learning technique for time series forecasting is applied on the data to predict the next values. The second stage consists in using a classifier to train the predictions obtained through the first approach and classify the prediction probability of each value based on the preestablished labels for each event and evaluate the final result based on the goodness of matching and the quality of matched predictions.

Figure 1. Hybrid Forecasting Classification Design

Threshold Setting

The two most popular distributions studied in the Extreme Value Theory EVT (Abdulali et al. 2022) were considered. Namely, the Generalized Extreme Value (governs the distribution of its block maxima) and Generalized Pareto distributions (concerned with the distribution of excess values over a certain threshold) (Abdulali et al. 2022; Castro-Camilo, Huser, and Rue 2022; De Zea Bermudez and Kotz 2010; Galib et al. 2022). The thresholding method considered is based on the estimation of the probability of events which offer a robust and flexible solution that does not depend on the distribution of the data. The minimum value resulting from the fitting of the GEV and GP applied on the dataset with an estimation of 0.5 percent of confidence is the threshold below which, any value is extreme.

Assuming the dataset as a sequence of observations $X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}$.

The fitting the GEV Distribution is characterized by three parameters (estimate using the Maximum Likelihood Estimation

(MLE) method): location (μ), scale (σ), and shape (ξ).

The cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the GEV distribution is given by:

$$F(x; \mu, \sigma, \xi) = \exp[-(1 + \xi((x - \mu) / \sigma))^{-1/\xi}] \quad (1)$$

The fitting the GP Distribution is used to model the extreme values above a certain threshold. Assuming that values beyond the threshold follow a GP distribution, the GP distribution has two parameters (estimate these parameters using the MLE method): shape (ξ) and scale (σ).

The CDF of the GP distribution is given by:

$$G(x; \xi, \sigma) = 1 - (1 + \xi(x - \mu) / \sigma)^{-1/\xi} \quad (2)$$

To determine the threshold below which any value is considered extreme, any value that corresponds to the 0.5 percent quantile of the

fitted distribution is selected. This quantile is obtained using the inverse of the CDF.

$$T = F^{-1}(0.005; \mu, \sigma, \xi) \quad (3)$$

Once the threshold T (threshold) is determined, any value below it can be considered extreme.

Machine Learning Algorithms

Two sets of algorithms were considered. The first for time series forecasting and the second for classification.

For the first, the combination of the Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) (Ahmad Waleed Salehi et al. n.d.; Aravindpai 2020; Shrestha and Mahmood 2019) and the Long Short-Term Memory (LSTMs) (Elsonbaty, Elsadany, and Adel 2023; Murat Karakaya 2020; Shrestha and Mahmood 2019; Staudemeyer and Morris 2019) was considered, resulting in the used hybrid CNN_LSTM and ConvLSTM (Cheng, Wang, and Yang 2023; Chowdhury et al. 2022; Lu et al. 2020; Zhao 2020)

For the second, the XGBoost (Li et al. 2019; Memon, Patel, and Patel 2019), the Random Forest (Biau and Scornet 2016; Liu, Wang, and Zhang 2012; Rigatti 2017; Schonlau and Zou 2020), the Decision Tree (Charbuty and Abdulazeez 2021; Harsh H. Patel^{1*} and , Purvi Prajapati² 2018; Kotsiantis 2013) and the Naïve Bayesian (M. Vadivukarassi, N. Puviarasan and P. Aruna 2017; Maheswari and Pitchai 2019; Razaque et al. 2017).

Interpretability Techniques

Three popular interpretation methods to interpret the predictions:

a. Feature importance: In this hybrid context, this interpretability techniques aims to explain or reveal the importance of specific features or neurons within these models, making it easier to understand and trust the model's decision-making process. (Chakraborty et al. 2017; Hooker et al. 2019; Kim and Cho 2019; Wei et al. 2020; Wojtas and Chen 2020).

b. The "Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations" (LIME), used for the classification aspect. It is useful to explain the predictions of complex machine learning models in a locally interpretable manner (Ankit Tewari, Carles Mitjans Coma, and Tom'as Izquierdo 2018; Palatnik De Sousa, Maria Bernardes Rebuzzi Vellasco, and Costa Da Silva 2019) (Mao Yang, Chuanyu Xu, and Yuying 2022). (Palatnik De Sousa et al. 2019; Saumitra Mishra, Bob L. Sturm, Simon Dixon 2017; Zafar and Khan 2021).

c. The "Explain Like I'm 5" known as Eli5, is a Python library which is integrated with multiple frameworks that provides a comprehensive set of tools for explaining machine learning models and making them more accessible and understandable (Khanna et al. 2023; Vij and Nanjundan 2022).

Class Balancing Methods

Two common methods of balancing classes are considered, namely, the Class weight (technique used to assign different weights to the classes based on their imbalance) (Spelmen and Porkodi 2018) and Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique known as SMOTE (technique is an oversampling technique specifically designed to address class imbalance in generating synthetic samples for the minority class by interpolating between the feature vectors of existing minority class instances) (Wu et al. 2022).

Research Design

From the acquisition of data to the explanation of the performance of machine learning algorithms, each step considered in this study is illustrated in Figure 3.

Data preparation involved setting a threshold for extreme event detection, transforming data for supervised learning, and splitting it into train/validation/test sets. Data is scaled using MinMaxScaler, and regressors are trained for short-term forecasting. Events are defined based on predictions, and classification models are trained considering class imbalance (using class weight and SMOTE). Prediction probabilities, model performance metrics, and interpretability methods are assessed.

Figure 3. Activity Diagram

Data preparation involved setting a threshold for extreme event detection, transforming data for supervised learning, and splitting it into train/validation/test sets. Data is scaled using MinMaxScaler, and regressors are trained for short-term forecasting. Events are defined based on predictions, and classification models are trained considering class imbalance (using class weight and SMOTE). Prediction probabilities, model performance metrics, and interpretability methods are assessed.

Data

The BCI and CCI were obtained from the OECD official website(Anon n.d.-a, Anon n.d.-b). The country considered was the United States of America due to its large size compared to other countries. Table 1 provides the description of the dataset and Figure 4 depicts its timeseries representation.

Table 1. Description of the Dataset

Variables	Count	Mean	Std	Min	25%	50%	75%	Max
BCI	760	99.97	1.39	95.12	99.21	100.11	100.89	104.00
CCI	760	99.99	1.48	96.08	98.87	100.49	101.06	102.89

There are no missing values and all the values are quite close. The timeseries plot depicts the absence of trend and presence of stationarity, confirmed by the p-value provided by the Augmented Dickey-Fuller test which is below

0.05 for each variable. ($p_value_BCI = 5.237877118736921e-11$, $p_value_CCI = 0.016789104416045534$). The dataset is suitable for a time series forecasting without further preprocessing except the scaling.

Figure 4. Timeseries plot of the dataset and individual plots

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Metrics

Two sets of metrics were considered. For the regression,

- The mean squared error, mean absolute error, represented respectively in the equations (4) and (5).

$$MSE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (Y_{p,i} - Y_{a,i})^2 \quad (4)$$

$$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |Y_{p,i} - Y_{a,i}| \quad (5)$$

Where n is the number of samples, $Y_{p,i}$ is the predicted output and $Y_{a,i}$ is the actual output, $| \text{expression} |$ is the absolute value of the operation (Singla, Duhan, and Saroha 2022);

- The coefficient of determination (Zhang 2017), explained in equation (6).

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum (y_i - \bar{y}_i)^2} \quad (6)$$

Where $\sum (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2$ is the sum squared regression and $\sum (y_i - \bar{y}_i)^2$ is the total sum of squares.

For the classification approach, considering the Actual positives that are correctly predicted positives are called true positives (TP), Actual positives that are wrongly predicted negatives are called false negatives (FN), Actual negatives that are correctly predicted negatives are called true negatives (TN) and the Actual negatives that are wrongly predicted positives are called false positives (FP) (Chicco and Jurman 2020):

The following metrics were considered:

- The confusion matrix:

$$CM = \begin{pmatrix} TP & FN \\ FP & TN \end{pmatrix} \quad (7)$$

- The harmonic means of precision and recall (F1 score) represented by the equation (8)

$$F_1 \text{ score} = \frac{2 \cdot TP}{2 \cdot TP + FP + FN} = 2 \cdot \frac{\text{precision} \cdot \text{recall}}{\text{precision} + \text{recall}} \quad (8)$$

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+TN+FP+FN} \quad (9)$$

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \quad (10)$$

- The Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC):

$$MCC = \frac{(TP * TN - FP * FN)}{\sqrt{((TP + FP) * (TP + FN) * (TN + FP) * (TN + FN))}} \quad (11)$$

Results and Discussion

Python 3.10 was used on google colab. Keras was used to build the deep learning model and the scikit learn for the machine learning models. GEV and GP were used to define extreme events in the dataset and the genextreme and genepareto were called from the Scipy library.

Defining Threshold

The result provides that the GEV distribution is suitable to define the threshold (Table 2)

Table 2. Thresholding Result

Threshold	BCI	CCI
GPD	15.07888	15.02539
GEV	97.54904	97.32314

Figure 6. GEV Fitted Distribution

The GEV is fitting the two variables of the dataset compared to the GP (Figure 6). Thus, having the thresholds defined, through the pseudo code 1, events are defined (1 as extreme event and 0 as normal events).

Pseudo code 1:

Label = []

For values in data:

If values in data[‘BCI’] < GEV Threshold [BCI] and

values in data[‘CCI’] < GEV Threshold [CCI]:

Any common value below threshold

Label.append(1) #1 as extreme events

Else:

Label.append(0) #0 as normal events

New_dataset = Data + Label

Figure 6b depicts extreme events detected in the dataset following the pseudo code 1.

While a total of 88 values fell below the threshold (41 for BCI and 47 for CCI, as shown in Figure 6a), only 16 of these events qualified as "extreme" based on the study's criteria (Figure 6b and Table 2). This resulted in a significant class imbalance, with 744 normal events compared to only 16 extreme events (Figure 7a). After partitioning the data into training and testing sets, the class distributions remained imbalanced, as depicted in Figures 7b and 7c.

Figure 6a. Values below Threshold

Figure 6b. Detected Extreme Events

Table 3. Extreme Events in the Dataset

Months	BCI	CCI
1974-10-01	97.49	96.78
1974-11-01	96.37	96.66
1974-12-01	95.46	96.63
1975-01-01	95.12	96.79
1975-02-01	95.26	97.20
1980-04-01	96.32	96.19
1980-05-01	95.32	96.15
1980-06-01	95.28	96.56
1980-07-01	96.24	97.15
2008-10-01	96.92	96.94
2008-11-01	96.15	96.68
2008-12-01	95.72	96.67
2009-01-01	96.76	96.68
2009-02-01	95.99	96.65
2009-03-01	96.39	96.86
2009-04-01	97.00	97.32

Figure 7b. Histogram of Events in the Train Set

Figure 7a. Detected Events

Figure 7c. Histogram of Events in the Test Set

500 points are considered as normal events while 9 are extreme events, giving a total of 509 points for the train set which is 67% of the data set and for the test set, 244 are considered as normal while 7 are extreme events, giving 251 data points which represent 33 % of the dataset. This data will be utilized for prediction using the selected algorithms and the result of prediction will be compared to these values to evaluate their performance.

Figure 8a. Structure of the CNN_LSTM

Forecasting Algorithms

After preparing the data in a format suitable for timeseries forecasting for short-term prediction (one step ahead), and reshaping it to meet the shaping of the CNN_LSTM and ConvLSTM algorithms, the structure of these algorithms are as follows in Figures 8a and 8b:

Figure 8b. Structure of the ConvLSTM

Here are the key details of model architecture and training:

- CNN_LSTM:
 - Input layer: Conv1D with 150 filters, MaxPooling, Flatten, Time Distributed.
 - LSTM layer: 150 cells.
 - Dense layer: 100 neurons.
 - Output layer: 2 neurons (for 2 variables).
- ConvLSTM:
 - Input layer: ConvLSTM2D with 250 filters.
 - Flatten layer.

- Dense layer: 100 neurons.
- Output layer: 2 neurons.
- Common features:
 - Activation function: 'relu'.
 - Optimizer: Adam (default).
 - Loss function: Mean squared error.
 - Training: 100 epochs on 33% of train set.
 - Batch size: 32.

Table 4 summarizes the results.

Table 4. Forecasting Metrics

Models	RMSE		MAE		Accuracy	
	Train	Test	Train	Test	Train	Test
CNN_LSTM	0.26	0.31	0.067	0.099	0.96	0.93
ConvLSTM	0.27	0.25	0.07	0.06	0.96	0.96

Figure 9a. RMSE by Model

Figure 9b. MAE by Model

Figure 9c. Accuracy by Model

It appears that Figures 9a, 9b and 9c that the ConvLSTM performed better than the CNN_LSTM, especially in predicting the test

set. This result is better visualized on the Figures provided below.

Figure 9a. Actual vs Prediction with CNN_LSTM

Figure 9b. Error by points using CNN_LSTM

Figure 10a. Actual vs Prediction with ConvLSTM

Figure 10b. Error by Points Using ConvLSTM

The CNN_LSTM on the test set which tends to deviate from the actual data (Figure 9a) while the ConvLSTM depicts a better behaviour (Figure 9b). In trying to detect events in the predictions

provided by these models, it appears that, due to the error of prediction, their number were either increased or decreased. Figure 11a and 11b depicts this.

Figure 11a. Extreme Events in Prediction of CNN_LSTM

Figure 11a. Extreme Events in Prediction of CNN_LSTM

Figure 12a. Extreme Events in Prediction of ConvLSTM

Figure 12a. Extreme Events in Prediction of ConvLSTM

Both models were able to identify most of the extreme events in the training data, with ConvLSTM matching the original number perfectly (9) and CNN_LSTM coming close (12). However, their performance on the test set differed. CNN_LSTM generated extra false positives by predicting more extreme events than actually occurred (8 vs. 7). ConvLSTM, on the other hand, missed one genuine extreme event (6 vs. 7). While ConvLSTM missed one crucial event, its overall performance was more precise by avoiding false positives. The next step will involve using these predictions as input for classification algorithms to further analyze and refine the identification of extreme events.

Classification Algorithms

The hyperparameters of these algorithms, especially the one addressing the balancing of classes are provided in Table 5. For the rest, their individual default values were considered in the case of imbalance classes and SMOTE.

Table 5. Hyperparameter Tuning Values

Model	Hyperparameter	Value
XGBoost Classifier	Scale_pos_weight	7.44
Random Forest Classifier	Class_weight	Balanced
Decision Tree Classifier	Class_weight	{0: 0.509, 1: 28.22}
Naïve Bayesian	Priors	[0.98, 0.01]

Thus, their performance in each case is provided in Table 6 (Appendix 1).

Imbalanced class scenario:

- XGBoost and Naive Bayes top performers: Both achieve near-perfect AUC, TP, TN, and MCC scores.
- XGBoost: High precision and recall, low FN and FP.
- Naive Bayes: Perfect AUC, precision, and recall. Captures all extreme events.

- Balancing with SMOTE: Improves AUC and other metrics compared to class weight.

Performance Explanation

Layers Feature Importance

The contribution of each layer of the forecasting model is provided in Table 7.

Table 7. Layer Importance by Model

CNN_LSTM		ConvLSTM	
Layer feature importance			
CNN layer		ConvLSTM2D layer	
Max	0.13	Max	0.14
Min	1.49E-05	Min	1.93E-05
Length	150	Length	1000
Range	0.13	Range	0.14
LSTM layer		Dense layer	
Max	0.096	Max	0.08
Min	0.07	Min	0.06
Length	100	Length	100
Range	0.02	Range	0.02
Dense layer			
Max	0.096		
Min	0.07		
Length	100		
Range	0.02		

Based on this result, here are some observations:

- CNN layers contribute similarly to prediction in both CNN_LSTM and ConvLSTM models.
- LSTM and Dense layers in CNN_LSTM have comparable importance, suggesting similar roles.
- Dense layer in ConvLSTM contributes slightly less than in CNN_LSTM.

Figures 11a and 11b visualize these variations.

Figure 11a. Layer Feature Importance of the CNN_LSTM

Figure 11b. Layer Feature Importance of the ConvLSTM

ConvLSTM outperforms other architectures due to its ability to capture complex data patterns, demonstrating the importance of layer choice and feature length in model performance. While increasing feature length can be computationally demanding, it can also significantly enhance model accuracy when well-suited to the data and algorithm.

Lime

For each model, the Lime method was employed to understand each instance-based forecasting. Considering the large number of experiments, only the result of the CNN_LSTM for each scenario is presented in Table 8.

Table 8. Lime Explanation (Sample)

Class mode	Feature values		Event Label	Prediction Probabilities	Event Prediction	Feature importance
Imbalanced	BCI	97.54	Normal	0.65	Normal	BCI <= 98.96 0.04153259992691054
	CCI	97.23		0.35		CCI <= 99.16 0.041361455728059715
	BCI	96.28	Extreme	0.007	Extreme	BCI <= 98.96 0.04354917856150617
	CCI	96.79		0.99		CCI <= 99.16 0.044212174932546436
Class weight	BCI	97.54	Normal	0.65	Normal	BCI <= 98.96 0.04559204353537988
	CCI	97.23		0.35		CCI <= 99.16 0.04571794524001884
	BCI	96.28	Extreme	0.007	Extreme	BCI <= 98.96 0.04354917856150617
	CCI	96.79		0.99		CCI <= 99.16 0.044212174932546436

SMOTE	BCI	97.54	Normal	0.1	Extreme	97.14 < BCI <= 100.05	-0.34421242405699454
	CCI	97.23		0.9		96.99 < CCI <= 97.54	0.26129559029473703
	BCI	96.28	Extreme	1.40E-04	Extreme	95.75 < BCI <= 97.14	0.3730538789119856
	CCI	96.79		1.00E+00		CCI <= 96.99	0.3440073200257691

Table 8 highlights key prediction details for each class mode. Feature importance values reveal their contribution to predictions. While model performance remains consistent with imbalanced and class-weighted data, SMOTE introduces a misclassification error for a BCI value of 97.54, incorrectly predicting an Extreme event. This error is linked to a negative feature importance for a specific BCI range, suggesting a misalignment between SMOTE-generated samples and the underlying data distribution. SMOTE's potential limitations in capturing complex minority class distributions and potential introduction of unrealistic samples could contribute to such misclassifications.

Table 9. Eli5 Feature Weights

Balance mode	BCI weight	CCI weight
Imbalanced	0.0004 ± 0.0063	0.0020 ± 0.0043
Class weight	0.0004 ± 0.0063	0.0020 ± 0.0043
SMOTE	0.2518 ± 0.0261	0.2175 ± 0.0106

The BCI and CCI weights have relatively low importance in the Naive Bayesian model's predictions, suggesting their limited impact on the target variable (Table 9). While SMOTE increases their feature importance, it risks misinterpretation due to the use of synthetic data.

Findings

- Feature importance and model performance depend on data and algorithm choice.
- ConvLSTM's greater feature length offers advantages for complex cases.

- Algorithm capability often outweighs class balancing for extreme event prediction.
- Careful selection of balancing techniques is crucial for trustworthy predictions in imbalanced datasets.

Conclusion

Trustworthy predictions are crucial in machine learning, but understanding how algorithms work can be tricky. This study digs into the challenges of interpreting predictions for imbalanced data, especially when it comes to extreme events like financial crashes or natural disasters. Many assume imbalanced data means worse predictions. But balancing it can also create complications. This study shows that the most important factors for accurately predicting and detecting extreme events are the data itself and the chosen algorithm. Balancing techniques actually have less impact, and might even mislead the model. It is important to note that this study was not about predicting specific events; it was about building a framework for analyzing extreme events using machine learning. While the limited data means the results are not universally applicable, they offer valuable insights into tackling imbalanced data in extreme event prediction. This field requires domain-specific knowledge, so future research will focus on long-term forecasting to identify more factors that define extreme events. This includes things like their duration, which is a big challenge in itself.

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Appendix 1

Table 6. Result of Classification

	AUC	TP	FN	FP	TN	MCC	Prec 0	Prec 1	Recall 0	Recall 1	F1 score 0	F1 score 1	Support 0	Support 1	Accuracy
Using prediction of the CNN_LSTM															
<i>Imbalanced</i>															
XGBoost	1	243	0	1	7	0.933	1	1	1	0.88	1	0.93	243	8	1
Random Forest	0.99	236	7	1	7	0.647	1	0.5	0.97	0.88	0.98	0.64	243	8	0.97
Tree	0.94	243	0	1	7	0.933	1	1	1	0.88	1	0.93	243	8	1
Naïve Bayes	1	243	0	0	8	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	243	8	1
<i>Class weight</i>															
XGBoost	1	243	0	1	7	0.933	1	1	1	0.88	1	0.93	243	8	1
Random Forest	0.99	243	0	1	7	0.933	1	1	1	0.88	1	0.93	243	8	1
Tree	0.94	243	0	1	7	0.933	1	1	1	0.88	1	0.93	243	8	1
Naïve Bayes	1	243	0	0	8	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	243	8	1
<i>SMOTE</i>															
XGBoost	0.99	243	0	1	7	0.933	1	1	1	0.88	1	0.93	243	8	1
Random Forest	1	243	0	0	8	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	243	8	1
Tree	0.94	243	0	1	7	0.933	1	1	1	0.88	1	0.93	243	8	1
Naïve Bayes	1	243	0	0	8	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	243	8	1
Using Prediction of the ConvLSTM															
<i>Imbalance</i>															
XGBoost	0.99	244	1	0	6	0.92	1	0.86	1	1	1	0.92	245	6	1
Random Forest	1	241	4	0	6	0.768	1	0.6	0.98	1	0.99	0.75	245	6	0.98
Tree	0.83	245	0	2	4	0.81	0.99	1	1	0.67	1	0.88	245	6	0.99

Naïve Bayes	1	244	1	0	6	0.92	1	0.86	1	1	1	0.92	245	6	1
<i>Class weight</i>															
XGBoost	0.99	244	1	0	6	0.92	1	0.86	1	1	1	0.92	245	6	1
Random Forest	1	244	1	0	6	0.92	1	0.86	1	1	1	0.92	245	6	1
Tree	0.99	244	1	0	6	0.92	1	0.86	1	1	1	0.92	245	6	1
Naïve Bayes	1	244	1	0	6	0.92	1	0.86	1	1	1	0.92	245	6	1
<i>SMOTE</i>															
XGBoost	1	244	1	0	6	0.92	1	0.86	1	1	1	0.92	245	6	1
Random Forest	0.99	244	1	0	6	0.92	1	0.86	1	1	1	0.92	245	6	1
Tree	0.99	244	1	0	6	0.92	1	0.86	1	1	1	0.92	245	6	1
Naïve Bayes	1	244	1	0	6	0.92	1	0.86	1	1	1	0.92	245	6	1